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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Herpes zoster ophthalmicus (HZO), a rare manifestation of varicella-zoster virus (VZV) reactivation involving the ophthalmic branch of the trigeminal nerve, constitutes approximately 4–20% of all herpes zoster cases. Prompt diagnosis and antiviral therapy are crucial to prevent ocular complications and long-term morbidity.

Case Presentation: In this report, we present a case of HZO in a 64-year-old immunocompetent woman, whose diagnosis was delayed due to the atypical onset of the rash. The patient had persistent headache and a delayed-onset periorbital rash.

Discussion: HZO was diagnosed based on clinical progression, and antiviral therapy led to improvement.

Conclusion: This case underlines the importance of a thorough clinical evaluation, especially in patients presenting with persistent headache and periorbital rash.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Eruption, headache, herpes zoster ophthalmicus

INTRODUCTION

Herpes zoster ophthalmicus (HZO) is a reactivation of the latent varicella-zoster virus (VZV) in the ophthalmic division (V1) of the trigeminal nerve (Sanayama et al., 2024). Clinical manifestations range from mild cutaneous eruptions to serious ocular complications, including keratitis, uveitis, optic neuritis, and, rarely, cavernous sinus involvement (Feist et al., 2024). Although HZO is more common in elderly and immunocompromised individuals, it may also present in immunocompetent patients, often with non-specific symptoms leading to diagnostic delays (Litt et al., 2024). This case report describes an unusual presentation of HZO in a healthy adult and emphasizes the importance of early recognition and treatment.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 64-year-old female presented to the Family Medicine outpatient clinic of Bezmialem Vakıf University with complaints of a persistent headache and a progressive rash surrounding the left eye. She reported no history of chronic illnesses, immunosuppressive therapy, or recent systemic infection. Her only significant surgical history included bilateral tear duct obstruction surgery and three cesarean sections. The patient denied any prodromal fever or malaise.

On physical examination, a crusted vesiculopapular rash was noted along the left periorbital region, corresponding to the dermatome of the ophthalmic nerve. Neurological assessment showed no focal deficits, with preserved consciousness, orientation, and cranial nerve integrity.

Ophthalmologic evaluation revealed mild conjunctival injection without corneal involvement. Pupils were isochoric and reactive; fundus examination was within normal limits. Eye movements and visual acuity were unaffected.

Vital signs were stable with a body temperature of 36.4 °C and blood pressure of 121/82 mm Hg. Laboratory analysis revealed a slightly reduced eGFR (77 mL/min/1.73 m²) and vitamin D deficiency (15.64 µg/L). All other hematological and biochemical parameters were within reference ranges.

One week prior to this consultation, the patient had been evaluated by internal medicine for forehead redness following minor trauma by a tree branch. She was prescribed oral amoxicillin-clavulanate, but the rash expanded and was accompanied by persistent headache. Cranial MRI showed no intracranial pathology except mild mucosal thickening of the maxillary sinuses (Figure 1). The patient reported a history of animal husbandry. Wound cultures grew sparse colonies of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella oxytoca*, with no indication of *Bacillus anthracis*.

Figure 1

Cranial MR; Mucosal thickening consistent with sinusitis in both maxillary sinuses

Based on the clinical presentation and distribution of the rash, HZO was diagnosed. The patient was treated with oral valaciclovir (1000 mg three times daily for 7 days), paracetamol for analgesia, and vitamin B12 supplementation. Significant clinical improvement was observed at the one-week follow-up, with resolution of the headache and marked regression of the rash (Figure 2). The patient provided written informed consent for the use of clinical images and publication of this case report.

Figure 2

Comperative analysis of eruption in the left periorbital region

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates the diagnostic challenges posed by atypical HZO presentations. While most HZO cases are characterized by an initial prodrome followed by a dermatomal rash, up to 20% may present with isolated headache or neuralgia before the cutaneous eruption becomes evident (Sanayama et al., 2024). The absence of overt ocular findings and the initial attribution of symptoms to trauma led to a delay in antiviral initiation. Delayed diagnosis increases the risk of complications, such as postherpetic neuralgia, secondary bacterial infection, and ocular damage (Litt et al., 2024). Although our patient remained immunocompetent, her age and potential stressors, such as animal exposure, may have contributed to viral reactivation. Notably, recent reports suggest that trauma or dermatologic irritation in the V1 dermatome may act as a local trigger (Sanayama et al., 2024).

Imaging studies such as MRI are primarily employed to rule out alternative neurological causes, including intracranial lesions or sinus pathology. In this patient, MRI findings were nonspecific and did not explain the clinical picture. As emphasized in the literature, accurate dermatomal mapping of the rash is often key to diagnosis (Feist et al., 2024).

Treatment with high-dose antiviral therapy within 72 hours of rash onset significantly reduces viral replication, symptom duration, and ocular sequelae. Although our patient received valaciclovir beyond this window, she still experienced a favorable outcome, likely due to the absence of deep ocular involvement. Adjunctive therapy with analgesics and vitamin supplementation may further support recovery (Feist et al., 2024; Litt et al., 2024). Physicians should maintain a high index of suspicion for HZO in patients presenting with unilateral headache and periorbital rash, particularly when initial treatment fails to improve symptoms. A biopsychosocial approach and thorough history-taking -integral to the Family Medicine perspective- played a central role in this patient's eventual recovery.

Herpes zoster ophthalmicus, though uncommon, must be considered in the differential diagnosis of persistent periorbital rashes and headache. Early recognition, timely initiation of antiviral therapy, and multidisciplinary evaluation can prevent serious complications. This case underscores the value of a comprehensive approach in diagnosing rare but treatable dermatoneurological conditions.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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